

Recommendations for performing aerodynamic field measurements on wind turbine rotors

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1 Introduction, background and motivation

Conventional experimental programs on wind turbines typically measure the integrated, total loads on the blades or rotor. These loads include both aerodynamic and mass-induced components, integrated over a specific spanwise length. However, such measurements lack detailed insights into the flow physics. When using these measurements to validate design codes, they can lead to misleading conclusions. For instance, a comparison between calculated and measured rotor shaft torque in [1] shows a very good agreement. This suggests that the code is accurate, but in reality, the good agreement was due to compensating errors, in this case an overprediction in lift offset by an overprediction in drag in combination with an underprediction of loads at the root being off-set by an overprediction at the outer part.

Hence the causes for discrepancies between calculated and measured loads can only be found with experiments which reveal the aerodynamic details on wind turbine blades. In such detailed aerodynamic experiments the pressure distributions at different locations along the rotor blades are anyhow 'need to know'. From these pressure distributions the local aerodynamic forces normal and tangential to the chord and so the aerodynamic load distribution along the blade can be derived. Additionally measurements of the local blade inflow (in the very close vicinity of the blade) and boundary layer information e.g. transition or even measurements of total drag enhance the understanding of the wind turbine aerodynamics and so they are very nice to know. Obviously, traditional measurements such as blade root bending moments and power continue to offer valuable insights in particular in combination with detailed aerodynamic properties.

Finally these detailed aerodynamic experiments should be complemented with measurements of the operational and meteorological conditions.

An important requirement for such aerodynamic experiments is that they are done in open domain.

Many detailed aerodynamic measurements are done on wind turbines placed in the wind tunnel. Examples include the NREL Phase VI measurements on a 10-meter diameter turbine in the world's largest wind tunnel, the NASA-Ames wind tunnel (Figure 2), and the EU project Mexico experiment, where a 4.5-meter diameter turbine was tested in the German-Dutch Wind Tunnel DNW (Figure 3).

In contrast, the number of publicly available detailed aerodynamic measurements in open-air remains limited. In the 1990s, IEA Tasks 14 and 18, [2], compiled data from five open-air aerodynamic measurements into a database. However, the turbines of that era were relatively small, (mostly diameters of 10 meter, see the example given in figure 1, while one turbine had a diameter of 27 meter). Around 2010, the Danish DanAero experiment was conducted on an 80-meter diameter, 2.3 MW turbine, significantly larger than those studied in Tasks 14/18. The data were publicly released around 2018 and analyzed during the final phase of IEA Task 29 [3].

Figure 1: TUDelft turbine in IEA Task 18

More recently, several countries have initiated or are currently conducting large-scale, detailed aerodynamic measurement programs. These countries cooperate within the framework of IEA Task 47. However, the number of open-air aerodynamic experiments on wind turbines remains limited, hindering the development of significant practical experience in these measurements. Additionally, many of these experiments were conducted over three decades ago, leading to a loss of critical knowledge and expertise. At the same time it is important to recognize the specialized nature of these measurements and the many technical challenges involved. These include drilling non-intrusive pressure holes in blades, selecting appropriate pressure transducers and data acquisition systems, ensuring proper sensor placement and power supply, protecting sensors from environmental factors, calibration of sensors etc.

By sharing the limited experiences available within the wind energy community on this specialized

Figure 2: NREL Phase VI turbine in NASA Ames wind tunnel

Figure 3: Setup of Mexico turbine in the measurement section of the DNW LLF

field, future experimentalists can avoid reinventing the wheel, so that progress in this area is accelerated. The primary goal of this document is to facilitate this knowledge-sharing process and document relevant experiences.

The document is structured as follows: Section 2 addresses practicalities of aerodynamic measurements at (mainly) rotating conditions. Although many of the considerations from section 2 have relevance for standstill conditions as well, it should be realized that standstill presents unique requirements in various aspects compared to measurements at rotation. These requirements are reported in section 3.

It is also important to realize the above mentioned requirement that the aerodynamic experiments should be done in open domain. Public in this sense does not only refer to the measurement data but for validation purposes it is equally important that the underlying turbine model description is public

Figure 4: Sketch of the instrumented DanAero blade

Figure 5: DanAero turbine with the test blade installed

too which is usually not the case. Several issues with regard to confidentiality of data are reported in section 4.

2 Experiences/issues on aerodynamic measurements at rotating conditions

2.1 Introduction

In this chapter several practical experiences are reported which were gained in aerodynamic measurements under rotating conditions.

The chapter starts with a study on optimal location of pressure sensors along the airfoil in section 2.2. Then section 2.3 discusses pressure scanner measurements, which measure the pressures relative to a reference pressure. Absolute pressure measurements are discussed in section 2.4. Within TURBINIA several new pressure measurement techniques have been developed, e.g. the AeroSense system from OST, section 2.4.2 and a pressure belt from DTU, section 2.5. In section 2.6 the processing of pressure distributions into e.g. aerodynamic coefficients are discussed where section 2.7 discusses the angle of attack at rotating conditions. Until now most of the attention in aerodynamic field experiments lies on measuring pressures but viscous information is important too. A limited number of experiments detected boundary layer transition on rotating blades where also the drag has been measured with a wake rake, see sections 2.8 and 2.9 respectively. Finally section 2.10 describes the importance of good inflow measurements.

2.2 Location of pressure sensors along the airfoil: Some recommendations

When conducting pressure measurements, the number of sensors and their placement on the blade surface has an influence on the accuracy with which aerodynamic quantities, such as the pressure distribution and resulting pressure forces, can be measured. In many experimental setups, this accuracy is ensured by simply using a large number of sensors. However, field experiments on wind turbines often feature limited access due to internal structures and the blade's scale. Furthermore, the application of a large number of sensors could raise structural concerns. Finally, the cost of the measurement equipment might limit the number of allowable sensors. In such situations, the placement of the pressure sensors needs to be planned carefully to achieve high-quality measurements.

There is a consensus in the literature that the density of pressure sensors should be higher at the airfoil's leading edge, where the gradients in the pressure distribution are often the highest [4–8]. In recent research, Fritz et al. [9] went beyond this first consideration and optimised the pressure sensor layout to represent the underlying pressure distribution as accurately as possible, even in varying operating conditions. This subsection will give an overview of the employed approach and its results. For the full methodology and analysis, the reader is referred to the original publication.

To optimise the pressure sensor layout, it is required to estimate

1. the operating conditions of the investigated cross-section, and
2. the pressure distributions resulting from these operating conditions.

The operating conditions can be derived using numerical simulations based on, for example, blade element momentum theory (BEM). If a turbine's rotational speed and pitch angle are known as a function of the wind speed, such simulations yield the angle of attack as a function of the wind speed. Furthermore, the results can be used to estimate the chord Reynolds number of the investigated cross-section. If the site-specific probability distribution of occurring wind speeds is known, this probability can be related to the occurring operating conditions of the regarded cross-section, too. The expected pressure distributions are a function of the angle of attack and the chord Reynolds number. They can be obtained experimentally using wind tunnel measurements or numerically, for example, based on computational fluid dynamics (CFD) or viscous-inviscid coupled panel methods such as XFOIL [10] and RFOIL [11, 12].

At this point, it is relevant to consider the objective of the pressure measurements. Most experiments aim at an as accurate as possible representation of the pressure distribution, which, in turn, guarantees a good estimate of the aerodynamic normal and tangential forces (normal and tangential along the chord). Fritz et al. investigated the ability of two optimisation routines (genetic algorithm and sequential quadratic programming) to place the sensors such that the pressure distribution is represented as closely as possible for a range of angles of attack. This was ensured by minimising the

deviation between the expected pressure distributions, which were simulated using XFOIL, and pressure distributions linearly interpolated between discrete sensor locations sampling the XFOIL results. This deviation was calculated for a range of angles of attack. By then weighting the error between interpolated and expected pressure distribution by the probability of an angle of attack to occur, the sensor layout was tailored to the expected operating conditions of the individual cross-sections.

The two optimisation routines yielded almost identical solutions for the sensor layout, indicating that an optimum solution exists for this problem. To evaluate the benefit of applying optimisation routines to determine the sensor spacing, the resulting accuracy in representing the pressure distribution and the lift coefficient was compared against that of a simpler, cosine spacing. A cosine spacing yields a higher density of sensors at the leading edge but takes no further aerodynamic characteristics into account. The optimised sensor layouts clearly captured the expected pressure distribution more accurately. Consequently, the lift and pressure drag forces can be derived from the measured pressure distribution with higher certainty. Despite being driven by the angles of attack with the highest probability of occurrence, the benefit of sensor layout optimisation was observed for large ranges of angles of attack. The differences between a cosine sensor spacing and an optimised layout and the resulting measured pressure distributions are shown exemplarily in Figure 6 for a case with ten sensors and the FFA-W3-241 airfoil at an angle of attack $\alpha = 6.75^\circ$.

Figure 6: Cosine vs. optimised sensor layout and the resulting pressure distributions

The results further demonstrated that with an optimised sensor layout, fewer sensors are required to achieve a desired accuracy (e.g., in lift determination) compared to a cosine sensor spacing. Consequently, the presented approach can contribute significantly to improving the data quality, reducing unnecessary equipment and saving costs in experimental setups.

A Matlab routine demonstrating the implementation of the two optimisation routines is openly available on the 4TU.ReasearchData repository [13].

In the original publication, the sensor layout optimisation approach was demonstrated on the generic case of the IEA 15 MW reference wind turbine to enable easy reproduction of the results. Since then it has also been applied to define the sensor layout for the Dutch TIADE field experiments carried out by TNO together with GE and LM, resulting in multiple months of high-quality pressure measurements [14]. For this application, additional boundary conditions were imposed on the optimisation routine to prohibit solutions placing sensors at inaccessible locations, such as the shear web and trailing edge regions. Furthermore, a minimum distance between sensors was enforced to ensure the structural soundness of the instrumented cross-section.

For those interested in optimisation of pressure sensor locations along these methodologies a Matlab routine demonstrating the implementation of the two optimisation routines is openly available on the 4TU.ReasearchData repository [13].

2.3 Measurements of relative pressures with pressure scanners

The most commonly used method to measure the pressure distribution around an airfoil is by drilling holes which are connected by means of tubes to one or more electronic pressure scanners with a very high scanning frequency (>10 kHz) so that the entire pressure distribution can be measured almost instantaneously. Such set-up is schematically presented in figure 7 (where it is noted that only a few tubes and 1 scanner are shown. Generally the pressure distribution is measured with say 15 to 60 holes where a pressure scanner may have 10-30 ports so that more scanners are needed to measure the full pressure distributions). As explained in section 2.2 the highest concentration of holes is applied near the leading edge, since this is the area with the strongest pressure gradients. An important aspect is that differential pressures are measured relative to a reference pressure. The reference port is generally connected with a tube to a reservoir in the hub where the pressure is assumed to be close to the atmospheric pressure. This implies an uncertainty in the precise absolute level of the pressures.

As mentioned in section 2.2, the resulting normal and tangential forces (normal and tangential with respect to the chord line) can then be found by integrating the pressure forces along and perpendicular to the chord, and then from the normal and tangential forces and the angle of attack (which is far from straightforward to determine on a wind turbine, see section 2.7) the lift and (pressure) drag can be determined

Figure 7: Airfoil with pressure taps connected to pressure scanner (only a few pressure tubes between tap and scanner are indicated)

The present section discusses several considerations and corrections which apply when measuring differential pressures.

Alternatively absolute pressures can be measured see section 2.4. It is noted that some of the considerations on differential pressures also hold for the measurement of absolute pressures.

2.3.1 Design of orifices, connections, (reference) tubing with uncertainties and corrections

Figure 7 shows the general set-up on how to measure the pressure distribution along the airfoils with pressure orifices and tubes without any details on the pressure orifices and the connection to the tubes. There are several details however which have impact. Amongst others the orifice disrupts the airfoil geometry and so it leads to a different static pressure than the real static pressure. Also flow effects inside the cavity below the tap and burrs (e.g. from drilling) or soiling particles near the edge of the tap may lead to disturbances.

In [15] an extensive literature analysis is carried out on the design of orifices with cavity below their connection to the tubes. It leads to the following recommendations:

- Smaller diameter orifices are less likely to cause premature transition, with boundary layer thickness offering a physically significant guideline for threshold diameter.
- To reduce susceptibility to premature transition, orifice cavity depth to diameter ratio should not be extremely large but at the same time not be too small where a minimum value of 2.5 is recommended to avoid exacerbating errors caused by tube connection sensitivities.
- Possibility of orifice edge burrs or soiling particles argues for larger diameter ports as error severity scales with the ratio of burr or particle height to orifice diameter.
- Pressure orifice rows should be angled relative to the mean flow direction to avoid the additive adverse effect of upstream orifices on downstream ones.
- The orifice row should be angled greater than 11 degrees relative to the mean freestream, to place orifices outside of the 11 degree half angle transition wedge. Due to the possibility of blade radial

flows angling the tap row inboard may be advisable. It is noted that this value of 11 degrees is larger than the angle found in the wind tunnel study, from [16] which showed a turbulent tap wake with an opening angle of 14° leading to a half angle transition wake of 7 degrees.

Moreover the pressure ports are connected to the pressure scanners with tubes where another tube connects the pressure scanner to the reservoir in the hub which is exposed to the reference pressure. For such differential pressure measurements with associated tubing the following effects need to be considered:

- Tube dynamics The length and diameter of the tube between the pressure ports and the pressure scanner need to be selected carefully in order to minimize the distortion on the frequency response of the pressure signal. Dependent on the length and or diameter of the tube the response at high frequencies may be damped, amplified or delayed. Generally a wider diameter and/or shorter tube amplifies the signal where a smaller diameter and or longer tube damps the signal.

The pressure response from tubes can be assessed theoretically with the program Premesys developed by the von Karman Institute based on the method from Bergh and Tijdeman [17]. It can also be assessed experimentally like it was done in e.g. [18] where a fluctuating pressure signal was generated as input to a pressure port connected to various tubes with a pressure scanner. As an example figure 8 shows the frequency response for a tube with a length of 1 meter and varying diameters. It can be seen that a diameter of 1 mm gives a good response up to frequencies of 40 Hz. A diameter of 1.7 mm amplifies the signal and a diameter of 0.8 mm damps the signal.

Figure 8: Amplification ratio from tubes, copied from [18]

The importance of reference pressure tube diameter choice is illustrated through experiences in the above mentioned TIADE project where initially a tube with an inner diameter of 1.45 mm was used. This however showed a delayed response to the expected pressure variation at a 'slow roll'. Such slow roll should give the hydrostatic pressure variation (see equation 1, below). However the measured response was very much different. A straightforward increase of reference tube diameter from 1.45 to 9 respectively 4 mm (dependent on the pressure scanner) gave the expected hydrostatic variation. More methodologies to correct for the delay and attenuation are proposed in [15].

- Hydrostatic correction. The sensor rotates with the blade, which means that the height is changing during one rotation of the blade, yielding a sinusoidal variation of the hydrostatic pressure with the azimuth angle according to:

$$\Delta p_{\text{hydrostatic}} \propto \rho g r \sin \phi_r \quad (1)$$

with r the radial position and ϕ_r the azimuth angle. This variation could represent about 40% of the aerodynamic pressure. It can be corrected relatively easy from equation 1 in case the azimuth angle is know.

- Centrifugal correction. In the rotating reference tube a pressure difference is created which balances the centrifugal force. The correction for centrifugal effects can be written as (see [15])

$$\Delta p_{\text{cent}} = 0.5\rho(\Omega r_{\text{sec}})^2 = 0.5\rho(V_{\text{tip}}r_{\text{sec}})^2/R \quad (2)$$

Hence for constant rotational speed the centrifugal corrections leads to a constant off-set in pressure signal .

- Purging of tubes. The tubes between the pressure holes and the scanners can (partly) be blocked from precipitation and dirt. Therefore several pressure scanners are delivered with an automatic purge system to clean the tubes. This purges system generally consists of a control system with a valve so that the tubes can be pressurized. In addition a compressor is needed. Moreover in the TIADE project a filter system was found necessary to clean the air of the purge system from dirt and moisture. Figure 9 from the TIADE project shows how purging improves the measurement of the pressure distributions.

Figure 9: Pressures distributions measured before (left figure) and after purging (right figure). Source: TIADE project

2.3.2 Selection of pressure sensors and their accuracy

Pressure transducers are available in different measurement ranges. When selecting the pressure transducers it is important to match this range to the expected pressures, where a margin is needed to avoid exceeding the limit (although experience has learned that this limit is not very critical, pressures can occasionally exceed the limit). At the same time, the range of the scanners should be selected such that they operate in the upper end of the range where the accuracy is highest. To estimate the pressures, it is important to understand that they scale with the dynamic pressure q , through C_p times q , see section 2.6.1). Now the dynamic pressure is:

$$q = 0.5\rho V_{\text{eff}}^2 \quad (3)$$

with V_{eff} the effective velocity at a blade section which can be approximated as:

$$V_{\text{eff}} \approx \sqrt{((1 - a) \cdot V_w)^2 + (\Omega \cdot r)^2} \quad (4)$$

Hence

$$q = 0.5\rho[(1 - a) \cdot V_w]^2 + (\Omega \cdot r)^2 \quad (5)$$

Where the axial induction factor will often be close to 1/3. Hence the expected differential pressures can be approximated from the anticipated wind speeds, rotational speeds, and an estimate for the pressure coefficient (C_p). They anyhow increase with wind speeds but in particular with rotational speed, i.e they are higher at the outer part of the blade so that usually pressure sensors at the outer part of the blade have a higher measurement range.

At the same time pressure scanner should be selected with the highest precision. The measurement accuracy is p_{acc} is interpreted such that $p_{measured} - p_{acc} < p_{real} < p_{measured} + p_{acc}$ so that the real pressure p_{real} is between the measured pressure $p_{measured} +/-$ the measurement accuracy. The precision of pressure sensors is commonly indicated as an absolute value, often represented as a percentage of the full-scale pressure meaning that the highest (relative) precision is reached closer to the sensor's maximum capacity. Hence although it is important for the pressure range of a sensor to be sufficiently large so that the expected pressures remain below the limit, it is equally important to avoid very low pressures since this yields a very poor accuracy. In the selection of pressure sensor in IEA Task 14/18 some participants (more or less arbitrary) targeted the specified accuracy p_{acc} to be less than 0.1 of the dynamic pressure.

An overview of the orders of magnitude expected on two typical wind turbines found in the literature are given in table 1. In this table an even higher accuracy of 0.01 is targeted. This table displays the theoretical wind speed and rotor speed for a 5 and 10MW wind turbines. It also presents the relative aerodynamic pressure at low wind speed (minimum wind speed at which the blades start to rotate), rated wind speed and maximum wind speed (above which the wind turbine stops rotating). These aerodynamic values are given at mid-span and at the tip taking into account an induction factor of 1/3. It should be noted that these values are here only to provide orders of magnitude and are not from accurate measurements.

Table 1: Orders of magnitude of expected aerodynamic pressure on a 5MW and 10MW wind turbine.

		adim	Prototypes	
			NREL 5 MW	DTU 10 MW
wind turbine properties	Hub diameter (m)		3	6
	diameter rotor (m)		126	178
	minimum chord (m)		1.4	
	maximum chord (m)		4.6	10
wind speed	minimum wind speed (m.s-1)		3	4
	rated wind speed (m.s-1)		11	11
	maximum wind speed (m.s-1)		25	25
rotor speed	minimum rotational speed (rpm)		7	6
	rated rotational speed (rpm)		12	10
	maximum rotational speed (rpm)		12	10
mid-span	minimum blade velocity (m/s)		23	28
	standard blade velocity (m/s)		40	47
	maximum blade velocity (m/s)		40	47
	minimum apparent wind speed (m.s-1)		23	28
	standard apparent wind speed (m.s-1)		40	47
	maximum apparent wind speed (m.s-1)		43	50
	minimum dynamic pressure	1	337	496
	average dynamic pressure (Pa)	1	1032	1410
	maximum dynamic pressure (Pa)	1	1253	1631
	peak aerodynamic pressure (Pa)	5	6264	8153
accuracy at 1% (Pa)	0.01	10	14	
tip	minimum blade velocity (m/s)		46	56
	standard blade velocity (m/s)		79	93
	maximum blade velocity (m/s)		79	93
	minimum apparent wind speed (m.s-1)		46	56
	standard apparent wind speed (m.s-1)		80	94
	maximum apparent wind speed (m.s-1)		81	95
	minimum dynamic pressure	1	1.3E+03	2.0E+03
	average dynamic pressure (Pa)	1	4.0E+03	5.5E+03
	maximum dynamic pressure (Pa)	1	4.2E+03	5.7E+03
	peak aerodynamic pressure (Pa)	5	2.1E+04	2.9E+04
accuracy at 1% (Pa)	0.01	40	55	
	Reynolds number at mid-span		4E+06	1E+07

It is noted that these numbers hold for rotating measurements. For standstill measurements the absence of rotation leads to a much lower effective velocity and so a much lower pressure level with associated poorer accuracy. This problem is addressed in section 3.4.

2.3.3 Requirements on sampling frequency: Some considerations

The minimum required sampling frequency depends on the objective of the experiment. Figure 10 provides an overview of the typical frequencies for various aerodynamic phenomena that can be studied. The rotational speed of the blades is directly proportional to their size, with a maximum speed of 1 Hz or 0.5 Hz (1 rotation in 2 seconds). The unsteady behavior of the dynamic stall can be categorized into two dynamics: dynamic stall resulting from blade pitching, or from the blade passing in the wind speed gradient in the boundary layer, or yaw misalignment. The orders of magnitude of such dynamics are therefore analogous to the blade rotation. The second dynamics is more local and is due to flow features such as the creation and shedding of dynamic stall vortices. These occur at higher frequencies than the pitching frequency (approximately 10 Hz on a wind turbine blade), as these phenomena appear only in a fraction of the complete dynamic stall process. The turbulence of the incoming atmospheric wind and the trailing edge noise have a relatively large frequency range. However, the frequencies that are typically of interest are in the range of 100 Hz and above. It is imperative to note that these frequencies are only orders of magnitude of the dynamics involved in a wind turbine. To accurately measure such dynamics, it is essential to attain a sampling frequency that is at least 10 times higher than the dynamics of interest.

Figure 10: Rough orders of magnitude of the dynamics involved on a wind turbine blade

If the focus is on time-averaged aerodynamic phenomena, the sampling frequency is of less importance. However, if the focus is on unsteady aerodynamic phenomena, the frequency of vortex shedding (f) is often considered the driving factor. This frequency can be estimated using the Strouhal number which non-dimensionalizes the frequency with the velocity component and the projected chord length (c).

$$St = f \cdot c \cdot \sin(\alpha) / (V_{\text{eff}}) \quad (6)$$

This Strouhal number is generally known to be in the order of 0.2 (see [19]) which makes the shedding frequency:

$$f = 0.2 \cdot V_{\text{eff}} / (c \cdot \sin(\alpha)) \quad (7)$$

Hence the shedding frequencies decrease with the size (and chord) of the turbine. Moreover the shedding frequency increases with radial position along the blade due to the higher effective velocities (equation 4), the smaller chord and smaller angle of attack towards the tip. Within the TIADE project the sampling frequencies were targeted to be 10 times the vortex shedding frequencies (with the consideration that a sinus is sufficiently accurate captured with 10 samples, see figure 11).

2.4 Measurements of absolute pressures

To obtain the aerodynamic pressure distribution on a rotating blade, absolute pressure sensors can also be used. There are three main categories of absolute pressure sensors. Fibre optic sensors (section 2.4.1) claim good accuracy and fast sampling frequency, but they tend to be expensive, and complicated

Figure 11: Sinus approximated with 10 samples

to install. Developments in Micro-Electro Mechanical Systems (MEMS) have brought low-cost, low-power pressure sensors. Barometers, similar to the ones used in our smartphones or smartwatches tend to be more and more accurate (± 50 Pa). Their sampling frequency is lower than pressure scanner or fibre optic sensors (about 100Hz). Fast Kulite pressure sensors as used in the Mexico wind tunnel experiments [20] are also an option. Like pressure scanners presented in section 2.3, absolute pressure sensors also need corrections and calibrations. Unlike pressure scanners, the correction methods tend to differ and the influence of each correction is also different.

2.4.1 Fibre optic sensors

Fibre optic pressure sensors are a developing technology to be considered for future aerodynamic measurements on wind turbine blades that could enable long-term measurement and validation campaigns not currently possible. Because fibre optic pressure measurements are a sealed system, water and dust cannot clog or disrupt the pressure measurement and they measure the pressure directly at the aerodynamic surface of interest. This eliminates the need for a purging system and it also eliminates the amplitude and phase errors as mentioned in section 2.3.1. Also by replacing power and data cables with fibre optic lines, the risk of lightning damage by adding metal cables to the blades is eliminated and makes it easier for wind turbine owners to approve their installation.

Fibre optic pressure sensors are Fabry-Pérot type interferometers where a membrane in the sensor strains due to the local pressure. The strain causes a shift of reflected laser light shown into the sensor by a fiber optic interrogator. This frequency change is calibrated by the manufacturer to static pressure. The details of the sensors physics are well described in [21].

This technology is new and therefore needs further development and testing to ensure accurate pressure measurements in wind turbine applications. There are currently no wind energy publications showing static pressure, lift, and drag measured from fibre optic pressure sensors compared to pressure tubing results either in the wind tunnel or on a wind turbine blade. A flight test has been conducted on an aircraft by [22] comparing one pressure port to a reference pneumatic tube which showed agreement for the single chord location measured.

Existing technology to be considered for development and application to wind energy aerodynamic measurements includes fibre optic pressure sensors from the company Luna innovation and from the company fos4X. Fos4X was later taken over by Polytec but they have now dropped out of the market. Fos4X sold fibre optic pressure sensors that are small with high frequency response. Fos4x specifications state steady pressure ranges of $\pm 20,000$ Pa which are well suited for wind turbine airfoil pressures on Megawatt scale turbines. Unsteady pressure measurements in the kHz range compared well with reference Kulite pressure sensors [21]. For installation or integration into wind turbine blades for aerodynamic experiments, the small 2 mm diameter size sensors could be internally mounted and set flush to the blade surface to minimize roughness and effects of transition propagating along the chord. As with all pressure sensors, access to the inside of a wind turbine blade by personnel or via access panels may not be possible, but the size of fibre optic pressure sensors may be small enough to enable completely external installation solutions. Within Task 47 Fos4X sensors have been applied by TNO

and Fraunhofer. TNO installed the sensors from the inside where Fraunhofer installed them from the outside. TNO and Fraunhofer both encountered issues with these sensors. TNO conducted a ‘slow roll’ at various pitch angles, comparing the measured pressure variation over a revolution with the known hydrostatic variation from equation 1. Unfortunately the measured variation did not agree to this hydrostatic variation and the measured variation was even found to depend on the pitch angle which is erroneous. A test in the TNO laboratory revealed that the sensor readings were sensitive to external stresses applied to the sensor housing. To mitigate this issue and reduce stresses, TNO mounted the sensors in wider holes.

Fraunhofer, on the other hand, employed a flexible adhesive to install the sensors, preventing stress-related problems. However, they observed significant drifts in sensor reading between consecutive slow rotations, even when they were performed shortly after each other. This required a calibration of the sensors every hour, contrary to the manufacturer’s claim of monthly calibration.

Luna Innovations offers the OS9100 fibre optic pressure sensors. This system has the advantage of easy integration with strain and accelerometer sensors and their existing fiber optic interrogator products. However their sensors are significantly larger at 9 mm in diameter than fos4x. This may present measurement errors when bending these sensors to be adhered to the leading edge of airfoils where the curvature is greater. The larger size also makes flush integration into the wind turbine blade composite surface more invasive. Additionally, the OS9100 has a minimum pressure of -3000 Pa, which is limiting for accurately measuring the suction peak of wind turbine airfoils near the leading edge, where -10,000 Pa is needed.

Cost is a challenge with fibre optic pressure measurements. Based on quotes from manufacturers originating in 2020, fibre optic systems are likely still thousands of Euros per pressure measurement channel when including the cost of the laser interrogator and data acquisition hardware. Whereas pneumatic pressure systems are hundreds of Euros per pressure measurement channel. However, the advantages of using fibre optic sensors given by the potentially reliable aerodynamic pressure measurements with high frequency response and reduced lightning risk may be worth the additional cost and development for a long-term data campaign.

2.4.2 MEMS-based pressure sensors

Micro-Electronics Mechanical Systems (MEMS) pressure sensors have the advantage to be produced in mass and therefore cost very little (on the order of 1 to 50 US\$ per piece). They are thin (less than 3 mm thick), low-power and can therefore be used wirelessly with a battery and be recharged with small solar panels ([23]). There is therefore no need of long cables running in the blade. As they are thin, they could be installed flushed to the blade surface with no tubings unlike pressure scanners. MEMS-based pressure sensors can also be installed on the blade, like in the Aerosense project [24, 25], as a thin sleeve around the blade. The main advantage is the ease of installation without the need of drilling holes into the blade.

As an example, for the Aerosense project, time-synchronised arrays of 40 absolute pressure sensors were installed along the chord on a section of the blade [26]. The chosen sensors were ST LPS27HHW from ST Microelectronics. They are water-resistant, only 2.7 mm thick and can measure from 260 hPa to 1260 hPa. They also possess a temperature sensor to compensate the main temperature fluctuations. According to the manufacturer, the absolute accuracy of the barometers is ± 50 Pa and a relative accuracy of ± 2.5 Pa which is barely enough to accurately measure the aerodynamic pressure on a wind turbine blade (see table 1: an accuracy of 1% at midspan corresponds to 10 Pa). But higher absolute accuracy can be achieved with the same sensors after thorough calibration. An example of a calibration process could involve measurements at different temperatures between -20 °C to 50 °C representing the range of temperature encountered by a wind turbine blade according to the IEC 61400-1 (ref). The pressure range should be of 800 hPa to 1100 hPa to take into account different atmospheric pressure and aerodynamic pressures that must be subtracted from the atmospheric pressure. With such a calibration the accuracy can go from 100 Pa of absolute accuracy down to about 10 Pa.

The sampling frequency of the MEMS-based pressure sensor is about 100 Hz. This is sufficient to capture the main pressure fluctuations on a rotorblade (see figure 10).

Table 2: Orders of magnitude of the pressures measured by absolute pressure sensors for a 5MW wind turbine

Measure pressures	Name	Order of magnitude	Ratio with dynamic pressure
Dynamic pressure	p_{dyn}	2000 Pa [200-7000]	1
Atmospheric pressure	p_{atm}	100 000 Pa	50
Daily atmospheric pressure variations	Δp_{atm}	2000 Pa	1
Pressure drift of barometers	Δp_{drift}	100 Pa/year	0.05
Hydrostatic pressure variation	$\Delta p_{hydrostatic}$	800 Pa	0.4
Acceleration pressure variation	K_{acc}	20 Pa	0.01

2.4.3 Corrections for absolute pressure sensors

It should be realized that all standard absolute pressure sensors are differential too, in the sense that there is always a pressure of reference, which in the case of absolute pressure sensors/barometers is a vacuum ($P \approx 0$). The pressure measured by the barometers is therefore the sum of the atmospheric pressure, the hydrostatic pressure and the aerodynamic pressure (see table 2).

Correction of the atmospheric pressure On a standard 5 MW wind turbine, the atmospheric pressure is about 50 times higher than the aerodynamic pressure. The atmospheric pressure can greatly vary over time with fluctuations up to 2000 Pa, as large as the typical dynamic pressure. The vacuum chamber in a barometer is never perfectly sealed, and a drift of the values up to 100 Pa/year can be observed according to the manufacturer. Each sensor does not measure exactly the same value, as they do not have the same reference (vacuum), and their drift might not be the same over time. Before installation, the sensors must be tested to estimate their drift during several days. The soldering procedure, the curvature of the electronics may also affect this drift. After installation, those corrections should be verified when the blades are not rotating due to lack of wind and the standard deviation of all the pressures below a defined threshold.

Correction of the hydrostatic pressure As mentioned in section 2.3.1 the sensor rotates with the blade, which means that the height is changing during one rotation of the blade, yielding a variation $\Delta p_{hydrostatic}$ of the hydrostatic pressure according to equation 1. Ideally, the hydrostatic pressure is corrected using an inertial measurement unit (IMU) which is composed of at least a gyrometer and an accelerometer installed at the same location than the absolute pressure sensors.

Specific fusion algorithm dedicated to wind turbine blades have to be used [27–30], because unlike more standard fusion algorithm mostly dedicated to drone applications, wind turbine blades experience a large centrifugal acceleration, 10 to 20 times higher than the gravity acceleration, that is not taken into account by most of the standard fusion algorithms. Such algorithms estimate the orientation of the blade, and therefore deduce the azimuth position of the blade. Hence from the azimuth position and the radial position of the sensor, the hydrostatic pressure follows from equation 1 with $\Delta p_{hydrostatic}$ which can be used to remove the hydrostatic pressure from the sensor reading.

$$p_{aero}(x_i, t) = p_{measured}(x_i, t) - p_{atm}(x_i) + \Delta p_{hydrostatic}(x_i, t) \quad (8)$$

Another probably less accurate solution could be to decompose the pressure signals into modes using FFT or maybe POD to extract the pressure fluctuations associated to the blade rotation frequency.

Influence of acceleration The MEMS barometers are composed of a small membrane that deforms due to the pressure difference between the two sides of the membrane (which is the vacuum chamber and the outside pressure). The mass of the membrane may be influenced by the acceleration. Figure 12 presents results of measurements done on a rotating carousel, on which absolute pressure sensors were installed and their port was clogged to only record the influence of the acceleration on the results. According to figure 12, the influence of the acceleration on the pressure reading is linear up to 24g, with a slope of 2.4 Pa/g. It means the sensors pointing upwards or downwards can read a difference of pressure of 4.8 Pa. For horizontal axis wind turbine, the centrifugal force is not normal to the

Figure 12: Influence of acceleration on the pressure measurements when the measurement hole is in the direction of the acceleration. The slope of the linear fit (in black) is 2.4 Pa/g.

membrane and can therefore be neglected. However, the influence of the acceleration should be taken into account for vertical axis wind turbine for example.

2.5 Pressure belt

As mentioned above in Section 2.3 the most commonly used method to measure the pressure distribution around an airfoil section of a blade is by drilling holes that are connected by means of tubes to one or more electronic pressure scanners. However, this requires access from the inside of the blade to connect the tubes to the pressure scanners. This access is possible in the inner part of a blade for a MW turbine but not on the outer part. Then a solution is to install pressure taps and pressure scanners during blade manufacturing as in the Danaero measurement campaign [31]. However, this is a complicated and expensive process to integrate into an industrial manufacturing process.

This was the background for the research and development work initiated at DTU 5-6 years ago with the overall objective to develop an add/on inflow and pressure measurement technique suited for measurements on full-scale turbines. For the pressure measurements, the old technique using a pressure belt was chosen. The method was used already during world war two, where it was found to be the most applicable, robust, and fast way to measure the pressure distribution on an engine cowling for investigation of the cooling [32].

Later, it has been used frequently within the aviation research community because it is considered a simple, non-destructive, and robust technique for measuring pressure distributions. One drawback with the technique is the distortion of the pressure fluctuations in unsteady inflow, where both damping and amplification of the response can happen depending on the frequency. However, different calibration methods have been developed for the reconstruction of signals.

The dimensions of the pressure belt are an important design parameter. An example is the study reported in [33] in which the objective was to investigate the effects of the size of the pressure belt tubing on the measurement of pressure distributions. Two pressure belts were mounted on the right wing of a single engine propeller-driven research aircraft. Inner diameters ranging from 0.7, 1.2 and 2.4 mm in combination with outer dimensions of 1.6, 3.2 and 4.8 mm were tested. Overall results showed good agreement between all dimensions at lower lift, whereas at higher lift deviations were seen for the bigger dimensions, in particular at the trailing edge region.

2.5.1 The DTU pressure belt

Different belt prototypes have been developed and tested since 2018. The first prototype had 15 pressure taps and the thickness of the belt was about 2.2 mm. After wind tunnel testing of the belt in the Poul La Cour (PLC) wind tunnel, the belt was installed and tested in June 2021 during a two-day campaign on the SWT-DD-120 turbine at the test field Høvsøin Jutland, Denmark [34], figure 14. This version of the pressure belt consisted of a printed fixture with a flat side and the other side with

Figure 13: Photo to the left: The belt manufactured with 19 copper tubes with an outer diameter of 1.0 mm sweated together. The graph to the right: comparison of the pressure distribution measured by the belt and with a standard tap instrumentation. Photo and figure from [32].

grooves where tubes with 1.68mm outer diameter and 0.86mm inner diameter were mounted. A hole (pressure tap) was drilled in each tube in the desired chord position, which was connected to a 16 channel mini pressure scanner (EvoScann). The miniature Pressure Scanner, with a size of 37 x 32.4 x 9.2 mm was used in a so-called calculated differential mode where one of the ports was used as reference. The full-scale range is -400 to 200 mbar with a resolution of 0.03 mbar. The scanner was glued/taped to the blade surface on the pressure side close to the trailing edge. Likewise, the pressure belt was glued to the blade surface in the chord-wise direction with a double-sided tape.

Figure 14: Left photo: The flyboard and pressure belt was installed from a lift on the SWT-DD-120 turbine at the Høvsøre test field in Jutland in June 2021. Right photo shows a close look at the flyboard and the pressure belt. Photos from [34]

Figure 15: Binned pressure coefficient distribution for flap on/off. Figure from [34].

The SWT-DD-120 turbine had flaps installed on one of the blades and a main objective with the installation of the pressure belt was to characterize the aerodynamic performance of the flaps. An example of the impact of the flap of the measured pressure distribution is shown in Fig. 15. A detailed analysis of the flap aerodynamic response has been reported in [35].

A major further step in the development of pressure belts was the design and manufacture of a 32 channel pressure belt. The new pressure belt is manufactured by extrusion in an elastic material that facilitates low-cost production after the one-time investment in the extrusion tool. The belt is 100mm wide and has 32 pressure channels of 0.8mm diameter. The maximum thickness of the belt is about 1.8 mm over the span with the channels and with a decreasing thickness toward the edges. In addition, the belt is produced with double-sided tape strips on the back for easy attachment to the blade surface. A single pressure orifice of about 0.7 mm is drilled into each channel.

To characterize the performance and accuracy of the pressure belt, it was tested in the DTU Poul la Cour Wind Tunnel (PLCT) [36]. The pressure belt was mounted mid-span along the entire circumference of a DU00-W2-350 airfoil section which additionally has a standard pressure measurement instrumentation of 97 orifices in a staggered configuration. The airfoil section has a chord of 1m, a span of 2m, a relative thickness of 35% chord.

An example of these validation tests is shown in Fig. 16, where pressure distributions are presented at three different angle of attacks. Except at the lowest angle of attack there is a very good correlation between the pressure belt data and the data from the standard tap instrumentation. The lift and drag polars shown in the upper part of the graph also correlate very well except for the post-stall lift where the belt measurements predict slightly lower lift.

Recently in spring 2024, the extruded 32-tap belt was used as part of the GE 1.5MW turbine instrumentation in the NREL downwind experiment [37] where the turbine was turned downwind, Fig. 17. Two pressure belts were installed on one of the blades in a position close to the tip and mid-span, respectively. In addition, a third belt was mounted on the tower at a height that matched the passage of the outer blade pressure belt.

For installation on the airfoil section the belt is cut to the desired length fitting the circumference of the airfoil section. The pressure channels are closed at one end and connected by exit tubes at the other end to the two mini pressure scanners mounted at the trailing edge; see Fig. 17.

An example of pressure belt measurements from the NREL downwind experiment is shown in Fig. 18. The time traces from the pressure measurements on the blade belt and the tower belt illustrate the very strong response when the blade passes the tower.

Figure 16: Results from validation tests of the 32 tap extruded pressure belt in the DTU Poul la Cour Wind Tunnel (PLCT) [36]. Configuration is Clean surface at $Re = 5E6$. Upper row: left: picture of model, centre: C_l curve, right: C_d curve. Lower row: uncorrected C_p left: $AoA = -10.0deg.$, centre: $AoA = 5.0deg.$, right: $AoA = 8.0deg.$.

Figure 17: Left photo: The extruded 32 tap pressure belt installed on the GE 1.5MW turbine at the NREL Flatiron test site [37]. Right photo: The pressure belt was connected to two EvoScan differential pressure scanners glued to the pressure side of the airfoil section close to the trailing edge. The scanners were then connected to the data acquisition system in the so called flyboard mounted close to the belt at the leading edge.

2.5.2 Summary

We have shown that the pressure belt technique successfully can be applied on a blade section in the wind tunnel as well as in the challenging conditions on a full-scale blade. Such pressure measurements are inevitable, e.g. for the future research on the impact of atmospheric turbulence on airfoil aerodynamics.

Figure 18: The graph to the left shows the time trace of selected pressure taps of the outboard pressure belt during tower passage. To the right time traces of several tower belt pressure taps during the same time interval.

2.6 Dimensional and non-dimensional loads from pressure measurements, dynamic pressure

It is common practice to non-dimensionalize aerodynamic loads into aerodynamic load coefficients. However the determination of these coefficients is not straightforward in the case of rotating wind turbine aerodynamic measurements. In order to understand this problem a distinction is made between experiments which measure differential pressures and experiments which measure absolute pressures.

2.6.1 Aerodynamic coefficients measured with differential pressure sensors

Differential pressure sensors measure the surface pressures relative to a reference pressure, usually located in the hub, where the pressure is typically not known. This introduces an uncertainty in the surface pressure measurement. This uncertainty is even more because the pressure in the rotor plane is ambiguous (at least according to simplified momentum theory see figure 19 from [1]).

Figure 19: Velocity and pressure decay in streamwise direction

uncertainty from this pressure jump $p_3 - p_2$ can be estimated by assuming an axial induction factor $a = 1/3$ (i.e. the value at design conditions). Then the pressure p_2 is according to the law of Bernoulli: $p_2 = p_1 + 5/9 \cdot (0.5\rho V_w^2)$. Similarly the minimum pressure p_3 is found to be: $p_3 = p_1 - 3/9 \cdot (0.5\rho V_w^2)$ so that the pressure jump between p_3 and p_2 is $8/9 \cdot (0.5\rho V_w^2)$. It is then reassuring that V_w is generally much smaller than Ωr , making this uncertainty in reference pressure relatively small compared to the dynamic pressure (q) at the blade section, which is according to equation: $q = 0.5\rho[(1-a) \cdot V_w]^2 + (\Omega \cdot r)^2$ according to equation 5. Since the dynamic pressure can be considered an indicator of the order of magnitude for the differential pressures this implies a relatively low uncertainty from the ambiguity in pressures near the rotor plane. However, this is less true at the inner part of the blade where the uncertainty is larger due to the relatively small Ωr .

The uncertainty in reference pressure plays a role in the determination of aerodynamic coefficients, because in many experiments the dynamic pressure q (with which the coefficients are non-

dimensionalised) is considered equal to the maximum value in the measured relative pressure distribution. Hence it is assumed that

$$q = p_{\max, \text{meas}} = p_{\max, \text{absolute}} - p_{\text{ref}} \quad (9)$$

with $p_{\max, \text{meas}}$ the actually measured maximum pressure (i.e. the differential value) and $p_{\max, \text{absolute}}$ the maximum absolute pressure. Note that $p_{\max, \text{meas}}$ may be based on a curve fit around the measured maximum values (in order to account for the limited resolution of pressure sensors) but this does not fundamentally change the method.

An alternative way of determining the dynamic pressure is offered by the 5 hole pitot probe measurements which are added to some experimental facilities. The resulting pitot pressure ($p_{\text{pitot, meas}}$ which is again measured relative to the reference pressure) has then been used as an estimate for the dynamic pressure:

$$q = p_{\text{pitot, meas}} = p_{\text{pitot, absolute}} - p_{\text{ref}} \quad (10)$$

Now the expressions 9 and 10 only give the correct values for q if the reference pressure is equal to the static pressure at the blade section but this static pressure is subject to the uncertainty given above.

An additional uncertainty, related to the unknown static pressure, appears in the determination of the pressure coefficients. In many experiments the nominator of these pressure coefficients is based on the actually measured pressure difference at a pressure tap, hence:

$$C_p = \frac{p_{\text{tap}} - p_{\text{ref}}}{q} \quad (11)$$

Again this is only the correct definition if p_{ref} equals the static pressure.

Hence the uncertainty in reference pressure mainly translates into the question whether this reference pressure can be used as static pressure in the determination of dynamic pressure and pressure coefficient.

A general method to account for the uncertainty in reference pressure (which also circumvents the problem of how to define the pressure coefficient) is given in [15]. Here the static pressure to which the maximum pressure in equations 9 and 10 are referenced is not the (ambiguous) pressure in the rotor plane but it is taken as the free stream pressure far upstream (or downstream), i.e. p_1 in figure 19. Moreover the stagnation pressure $p_{\max, \text{absolute}}$ from equation 9 is considered equal to the atmospheric stagnation pressure $p_{\text{atm, stagnation}}$

$$p_{\text{atm, stagnation}} = p_{\max, \text{absolute}} = p_1 + q_{\text{met}} \quad (12)$$

With q_{met} the dynamic pressure based on the wind speed measurements at a meteorological mast some distance ahead of the turbine where $p_{\max, \text{absolute}}$ is given by equation 9:

$$p_{\max, \text{absolute}} = p_{\max, \text{meas}} + p_{\text{ref}} \quad (13)$$

This makes the difference between the reference pressure and the static pressure p_1 (denoted as Δp_{ref}):

$$\Delta p_{\text{ref}} = p_1 - p_{\text{ref}} = p_{\max, \text{meas}} - q_{\text{met}} \quad (14)$$

This expression for Δp_{ref} is then used to correct the reference pressure in equations 9, 10 and 11.

In view of the uncertainty in reference pressure the dynamic pressure is sometimes derived theoretically from equation 5 (based on equation 4 for the effective velocity). Several procedures were followed to estimate this value of V_{eff} . Sometimes V_{eff} was determined straightforwardly as the vectorial sum of the free stream wind velocity and the rotational speed. Then it should be realized that for field experiments the value of the free stream wind velocity is not precisely known due to the stochastic atmosphere. Another uncertainty lies in the induced velocities. They are sometimes neglected or they are assumed to be 1/3. They could also be determined from an analytical model e.g. an inverse BEM or an inverse free wake method but these analytical methods are subjects to an uncertainty as well. Fortunately the knowledge of the reference pressure is not needed for the determination of dimensional aerodynamic segment forces. This can be illustrated by the integration of the pressure distribution into the normal force which for simplicity is written as an integration along the chord:

$$n = \int_{x=0}^{x=c} (p_{\text{pressure}} - p_{\text{suction}}) dx = \int_{x=0}^{x=c} (p_{\text{pressure}} - p_{\text{ref}}) - (p_{\text{suction}} - p_{\text{ref}}) dx$$

where the index 'pressure' denotes the pressure side of the airfoil and the index 'suction' denotes the suction side. Hence under the assumption of a constant reference pressure during the measurement of the pressure distribution, (which is a valid assumption in view of the very high sampling frequencies of pressure scanners) the absolute value of the normal force can be determined from the pressure differences and it is not disturbed by the uncertainty in the reference pressure.

2.6.2 Aerodynamic coefficients measured with absolute pressure sensors

The previous section refers to the determination of aerodynamic coefficients with relative pressures. In some cases however absolute pressure are measured. This can for example be done through fibre optic sensors, see section 2.4.1 but also in the earlier mentioned Mexico wind tunnel experiment, absolute pressures were measured with fast Kulite sensors. In this Mexico experiment the q was determined with equations 3 and 4 but as mentioned in 2.6.1 the determination of such dynamic pressure may be subject to uncertainties in the axial induction factor and free stream wind speed. This was less of a problem in the controlled wind tunnel environment of the Mexico project because the tunnel speed and so the free stream velocity is known much better than in the stochastic atmosphere,

Then from the dynamic pressure q the static pressure p_{ref} which is needed in the definition of the pressure coefficient (equation 11) is found with $p_{\text{ref}} = p_{\text{max,meas}} - q$ with $p_{\text{max,meas}}$ the actually measured absolute maximum pressure (where similar to the determination of the maximum pressure from differential sensors, section 2.6.1, a curve fit may be needed to catch the actual maximum pressure to account for the limited resolution of pressure sensors).

2.7 How to infer the angle of attack at aerodynamic measurements

The angle of attack (α) is a critical parameter in lifting line methods, as these models rely on airfoil data that are a function of α . In such methods the angle of attack is generally defined as:

$$\alpha = \text{atan}(V_w - u_i)/(\Omega r) - \epsilon. \quad (15)$$

With V_w the free stream wind, u_i the axial induced velocity, Ω the rotational speed and ϵ the twist. Note that for simplicity the tangential induced velocities are ignored and the pitch angle is assumed to be zero.

In a 2D wind tunnel, the angle of attack is straightforwardly known as the angle between the chord and the undisturbed wind vector which is aligned with the tunnel walls, see $\alpha_{\text{windtunnel}}$ in figure 20.

However, this straightforward approach is not applicable to wind turbines due to the absence of a comparable undisturbed wind velocity. At first sight the undisturbed wind vector far upstream of the rotor might seem like a suitable reference, but this neglects the induced velocity (u_i) from equation 15. These induced velocities are applied at the rotor plane which then suggests that measuring the angle of attack near the blade section would be more appropriate. However a physical measurement of the inflow angle near the rotor blade (e.g. through a five-hole pitot probe or a wind vane) yields an inflow angle which differs from the angle of attack. This can be explained by considering the flow angle measurement with a probe, which is placed ahead of the airfoil, in the wind tunnel, see figure 20. The figure shows that this measured local inflow angle indicated with α_{probe} is different from the real angle of attack indicated with $\alpha_{\text{windtunnel}}$, due to the 'bending' of the streamlines. This is caused by the presence of the profile itself, i.e. from the upwash which is induced by the bound vorticity.

In literature a huge number of methods can be found which infer the angle of attack, It is virtually impossible to explain them all but very roughly the techniques can be divided into three main categories:

1. Model-based methods
2. Data-driven methods
3. Hybrid methods

Figure 20: Angle of attack in wind tunnel environment

2.7.1 Model-based methods

Model-based methods rely on the evaluation of the flow around an airfoil to evaluate the angle of attack on wind turbine blades. Rahimi et al [38] present and compare model-based methods such as inverse Blade Element Momentum (BEM), averaging techniques, self-induced subtraction, and the vortex wake theory to obtain the angle of attack on a blade. Another self-induced subtraction method is proposed by Zhong et al [39] with a distinction between effective and nominal angle of attack.

A widely used method is the so-called Average Azimuthal Technique ([40]) which is based on annular average values of the axial velocity. This requires many data at several upstream and downstream locations of the rotor taken at (relatively steady) flow field data. In [38] a 3 point technique is described which is a modification of the Average Azimuthal Technique and which can determine the local blade angle of attack. This method too, although to a slightly smaller extent, requires extensive flow field data. The method from [41], is only valid for a 3 bladed rotor under axi-symmetric conditions. It makes use of the fact that for axi-symmetric conditions, the upwash from the 3 blades at the angle bisector of two blades is equally canceled out by which the value of the velocity at that position so that by definition the induced velocity remains! Moreover, model-based methods often assume aligned flow conditions by which yawed conditions are prone to more inaccurate results [42].

The above-mentioned requirements (high-resolution data, steady conditions, axisymmetric conditions) make it difficult to apply them in the field. Therefore, these methods are usually applied for wind tunnel measurements where the flow field can be measured with a much higher resolution (e.g. with PIV) under almost constant and axisymmetric conditions.

Inverse BEM method relies on empirical relations between the thrust coefficient and the induction factor, and, epistemically, should not be a part of the verification and validation process in line with the proposition of [1] *The use of theoretical models in the processing of measurement data reduces the value of these measurements as validation material for these methods.*

2.7.2 Data-driven methods

To overcome the lack of knowledge of the velocity field around the airfoil, purely data-driven techniques have further been developed to estimate the angle of attack in dynamic conditions, based on pressure measurements and regression or machine learning algorithms [43–45]. These latest examples have mostly been developed for drones and UAVs but not specifically for rotating blades. Moreover, data-driven models are trained using a large database, which is not always fully available or feasible to obtain.

2.7.3 Hybrid methods

Hybrid methods combine physics-based models with experimental data to improve the robustness of purely data-driven schemes and reduce their reliance on large amounts of data. For example, Sant et

al. [46] evaluate the aerodynamic force from the pressure distribution around a profile and estimate the near wake to deduce the angle of attack. Alternatively, many methods match the measured 3D rotating pressure distribution (or the location of the stagnation point, which can be considered a subset of the pressure distribution) to a 2D pressure distribution or stagnation point provided for different angles of attack. These 2D pressure distributions and stagnation points can result from wind tunnel measurements or airfoil code calculations, where the angle of attack is clearly defined.

An example of such method was already applied in [47], where the location of the stagnation point, determined from a curve fit on the pressure distributions around its maximum pressure near the leading edge region was used as an indicator for the angle of attack. Often, the location of the stagnation point is only weakly dependent on the angle of attack, so it is crucial to define the stagnation point location very precisely for different angles of attack. However, defining the stagnation point location precisely is challenging when it follows from a curve fit around the maximum pressure in particular when a limited number of sensors is available.

Marikovskiy et al. [48] developed a hybrid model to estimate the position of the stagnation point and the wind speed with only five differential pressure measurement locations by using an inviscid flow model around the leading edge. The sensors are encapsulated in a flexible housing, which can be easily mounted on any existing wing without damaging it.

Several other methods fit a larger portion of the pressure distribution. An example is the automatic pattern-matching method from [14], which finds the minimum deviation between the measured and calculated pressure distribution at various angles of attack through a pattern-matching algorithm. The pressure distributions are calculated with RFOIL [49] which takes into account 3D effects at (mild) stall. Using RFOIL partly circumvents a drawback of these fitting methods to 2D pressure distributions which is the fact that 3D or unsteady conditions might influence the pressure distribution in particular at large angles of attack. Still it does not fully eliminate the concern raised in the before mentioned proposition of [1] which states that using theoretical models in the processing of measurements reduces the value of these measurements for an independent validation of these models.

Another hybrid method, which typically combines experimental and model results, involves measuring the inflow angle in front of the leading edge at a specific point using a device such as a 5-hole pitot probe. However, as illustrated in Figure 20, the resulting inflow angle is not the angle of attack. To determine the angle of attack, the upwash from the inflow angle must be subtracted. Correcting for the upwash from a 3D blade is more complex than for a 2D airfoil, as it is induced by the bound vorticity along the entire blade, which is difficult to determine. Sometimes, the bound vorticity and resulting upwash are calculated from pressure distributions measured along the blade using the Kutta-Joukowski theorem. Since the local velocity, an outcome of this procedure, is needed in the Kutta-Joukowski theorem, an iterative method is applied to solve this system ([50]).

Alternatively, NREL determined the upwash from 2D wind tunnel measurements ([51]), making the probe method a fully experimental approach. The drawback of using 2D wind tunnel measurements lies in the 3D effects on a rotating wind turbine blade, which makes corrections from 2D measurements less valid.

2.7.4 Angle of attack: Concluding remarks

A variety of methods have been developed to determine the angle of attack on a wind turbine. However, many of these methods are less suitable for field situations because they require more detailed data than what is typically available from field measurements. As a result, these methods are often used in wind tunnel experiments.

For the remaining methods, it appears that under steady-state conditions, with relatively small angles of attack (i.e., below the stall angle), no yaw, and at mid-span, the agreement between methods is generally reasonable. However, when these conditions are not met, determining the best method becomes challenging.

Thus, the provocative proposition from [1] still holds true: *All investigations which aim to find the best method to measure the angle of attack in wind turbine aerodynamics are useless. There is no such angle of attack.* Nevertheless, it remains crucial to obtain a good indication of the angle of attack, as many aerodynamic models depend on this concept.

2.8 Measurement of Boundary layer transition

Investigating Boundary Layer (BL) transition on rotating wind turbine blades experimentally has some history dating back to the 1980ies. At that time a two-bladed research turbine (HAT-25, 300 kW rated power) was used, and a short report [52] was prepared but not published. Then (and now) microphones were used, where - in most cases - a sharp and sudden increase of sound-pressure-level (SPL) (sometimes a certain frequency range is filtered out) indicates transition from a laminar to a transitional or even fully turbulent state of the BL. During the famous DAN-AERO MW Experiments [53] temporal resolution could be increased to an amount that distinguishing between top and bottom location of the rotor blade was possible. As a result, the corresponding very different inflow conditions which directly influence onset of transition could be made visible.

Apart from microphones thermography is suited to detect transition. If the blade (the part on which transition is to be investigated) is prepared to an initial identical surface temperature, then the very different heat-transfer properties of laminar and turbulent BLs generate very quickly temperature differences which can be visualized. In [54] it was shown that both approaches (microphones and thermography) lead to the remarkable results of equal accuracy with regard to the location of transition.

Experiments on wings of aeroplanes, see for example [55–57] are rather similar but differ in one important respect: Most of the time an aero-plane is intended to operate in parts of the atmosphere where inflow-turbulence is very low, sometime even lower than in a wind-tunnel. This makes it necessary to use more sensitive sensors like hot films. These consist of an array of hit-wike like thin wires but glued directly onto a surface, thereby being sensitive to wall shear stress. For details see [56] In [58] it was tried to use this technique on a wind turbine blade, but - due to the very short (about 80mm out of 950mm chord) sensitive length - with a limited set of usable data-sets only. Further, in some cases a spurious peak was observed in the power-density spectra which could not related to fluid-mechanical phenomena and was most probably caused by too strong electro-magnetic noise, probably from the inverter-control units.

A particular feature of all these kinds of experiment is related to comparison with simulation using the e^N -method in combination with RANS-CFD [59]: To accurately predict the theoretical point (better: range) of transition a so-called N-Factor (which - roughly speaking - measures the distance from the point of first instability to a point of fully-developed turbulence) has to be provided. From wind-tunnel measurements an empirical correlation reads as

$$N(Tu) = 3.56 - 6.18 \cdot \log_{10}(100 \cdot Tu), \quad (16)$$

if Tu is given in % as the fraction of the standard deviation against average of some time-series of wind-speed. But here is the problem - in wind energy Tu covers a range of large (compared to wind-tunnel measurements) up to 10ths of % giving rise to unrealistic values from Eq. (16). An ad-hoc procedure would consist of introducing a low-frequency cut-off, assumed to be in a range from 10 to 100 Hz.

A deeper investigation and justification of using Mack's correlation for predicting transition on wind-turbine blades was undertaken in [60, 61] and resulted in a modification which might be able to substitute Mack's original version for use on wind turbine blades.

In spite of these rare investigations much more are necessary to reach for a more complete understanding. Some items to be addressed might be summarized as:

- quantify the inflow turbulence in more detail in short intervals,
- test wind-turbine blades using much more pronounced laminar airfoils, e.g. such which are known to have lift-to-drag ratio of more than 200 from wind tunnel experiments,
- use fast and reliable equipment which has low or no disturbing influence.

Figure 21: The instrumented blade section.

2.9 Measurements of drag with wake rake

The measurement of the total drag of individual airfoil sections on full-scale blades is a task which until now had not been feasible due to the complexity of instrumentation required. At wind tunnel level, the measurement of the total drag coefficient, including both the pressure and the viscous components, is usually performed indirectly by measuring the momentum deficit behind the airfoil using a so-called *wake rake*. However, the information about the drag and the lift-to-drag ratio of turbine blades during operation is a key parameter for the understanding (and improvement) of the aerodynamic performance of modern turbines.

This wake-rake measurement concept has been further developed to allow full scale measurement of airfoil drag during operation in a collaborative project between DTU Wind Energy and Siemens Gamesa Renewable Energy A/S¹. A publication of the results is planned but not concluded at the moment of writing of this document. For the purpose of this measurement, a customized wake rake was designed which could be used during operation. Some of the design requirements included the total weight of the system (to avoid rotor imbalance and to ease installation), the total size of the system (to simplify installation procedure and time), the structural stiffness (to minimize vibrations during operation). Furthermore, the wake rake was designed to capture a broad portion of the wake of the airfoil for the expected range of angles of attack. The data of the wake rake was acquired with a system similar to that described in [62]. The test turbine is a direct drive 4.3 MW machine with 120m rotor diameter of designation SG-4.3-120 DD. The instrumentation of the test turbine is discussed by [63]. In preparation for mounting the wake rake, interface pads were adhered to the blade in advance to serve as a support structure for the wake rake. These pads were engineered to bear shear and tension loads from the support structure, eliminating the need to drill holes in structurally critical areas of the blade. The complete system as installed is shown in Fig. 21. Its installation was performed in approx. 3-4 hours.

The testing campaign covers a period of two days from 28-07-2022 to 29-07-2022. During these days a number of individual tests were run while varying operational parameters of the wind turbine. Most tests were logged at a nearly constant rotational speed due to low wind on the night from July 28 to 29. Startup and shutdown cases as well as intentional yaw misalignments were also measured. An exemplary measurement is shown in Fig. 22

¹The activities were carried out within the VIAs project which was partially funded by the Danish public entity EUDP under research journal 64019-0061.

Figure 22: Exemplary measurement of C_p distribution, momentum deficit, lift, and drag, with data from the wake rake, as well as an additional pressure belt and five-hole Pitot probe.

In summary, the measurement of drag at full scale is seen as an important element in the validation chain of rotor aerodynamics, providing a link between the information collected at detailed wind tunnel level and the integral quantities measured at full-scale. However, this type of measurement is not simple to perform and further improvements in the technique would highly benefit the wind turbine community. The measurements performed as a part of the VIAs project is, as to the knowledge of the authors, the first of its kind. Further improvements to the technique are encouraged, as it will provide a valuable source of full-scale sectional aerodynamic validation data in the future.

2.10 Measurement of Turbulent inflow

This document focuses on aerodynamic measurement techniques and does not address the measurement of turbulent inflow. However, this does not diminish the importance of turbulent inflow. On the contrary, experiences from TURBINIA revealed several challenges in comparing calculated and measured time series results, primarily due to uncertainties in the wind input. The turbulent wind input was predefined in a turbulence box based on measurements from a meteorological mast. However, the relatively low resolution of the mast sensors limited the accuracy of this approach.

The new experiments in TURBINIA, which utilize LIDAR, offer significant potential. The much higher resolution of LIDAR wind speed measurements are expected to enable the generation of turbulent wind speeds that more closely align with reality.

3 Experiences/issues at standstill measurements

3.1 Introduction

This chapter focuses on the specific challenges of detailed aerodynamic measurements during standstill or idle conditions. While several considerations given for rotating measurements in Section 2 remain relevant, the distinct characteristics of standstill operations necessitate a dedicated discussion.

An important motivation for conducting measurements in standstill conditions is often to validate load response calculations for Design Load Case (DLC) 6.2. This load case represents standstill conditions during storms, a scenario known for its potential instability.

While measurements from integrated loads can also provide valuable insights for this load case (e.g. they can be used to identify vibration-sensitive conditions), they lack the detailed information on the aerodynamic mechanisms driving these instabilities. Thereto it should be realized that a rotor blade at standstill experiences a very wide range of angles of attack which amongst others include deep stall values and backflow angles near 180 degrees. The steady and unsteady aerodynamic behavior at these angles of attack which drives instabilities is still unexplored field where in addition turbines at standstill may be exposed to yaw misalignment, leading to cross flow along the blade, which adds further uncertainty. In order to understand the aerodynamic phenomena at these conditions detailed aerodynamic measurements are needed

3.2 Targeted conditions for standstill measurements

In order to define a test matrix for standstill conditions the effects from yaw, pitch and azimuth at those conditions have to be understood: The aerodynamics of a turbine at standstill is (apart from wind speed) for zero yaw largely determined by the pitch angle since it is the pitch angle which inversely proportionally determines the angle of attack. In case of non-zero yaw it is not only the pitch angle but also the yaw angle which contributes to the angle of attack where for azimuth angles unequal 0 and 180 degrees the yaw angle leads to a cross-flow along the blade. The targeted wind speed is also important. Thereto the main reason for experiments in standstill has to be recalled which is to validate load case DLC 6.2, i.e. the load case where the turbine is parked at wind speeds above cut-out, i.e. at very high wind speeds. Such high wind speeds present two significant challenges. Firstly, these experiments focus on events with potential structural integrity concerns (vibrations during storms). This necessitates a rigorous risk assessment, especially when seeking permission from manufacturers. Secondly, storms are rare events, making it difficult to plan and conduct measurements within a reasonable timeframe. In this context, it can be argued that standstill measurements at lower wind speeds can still offer valuable insights for validating aerodynamic models since key drivers for uncertainty in these models, such as large unconventional angles of attack and cross-flow effects, can also be achieved at low wind speeds through adjustments to the blade pitch angle, azimuth angle, and yaw angle. Additionally the structural vibrations at lower wind speeds will be limited. On hand this makes the response less representative for the storm load case but on the other hand it is beneficial since the reduced vibrations eliminates many uncertainties from the structural dynamics so that the interpretation of measurements from an aerodynamic perspective is facilitated. Still high wind speeds are essential to capture the aero-elastic behavior under real-world storm conditions, as they influence the interaction between aerodynamics and structural dynamics (including Reynolds number effects). Another advantage of high winds lies in the higher dynamic pressures and so a higher accuracy of the pressure reading, see section 3.4. As such there are many counteracting arguments: On one hand there is a desire for high wind speeds; on the other hand, the many potential combinations of pitch angles and azimuth angles make it virtually impossible to capture them all at the rare high wind speeds within a feasible measurement time. This implies a need to prioritize the targeted conditions, where the annual wind speed distribution for the site can assist in planning a realistic test matrix within the given time constraints even though the wind climate is uncontrollable, and exceptions are possible. As an example the test matrix from the Dutch TIADE project started with the definition of two "need to have" traverses: A pitch traverse at zero yaw and a yaw traverse at a feathered pitch angle where in addition several "nice to have" situations been defined.

In order to define a test matrix which include data points at rare high wind speeds, the required time per data point is crucial information to evaluate the number of data points that can realistically be expected within the available time. For data points aiming at measuring vortex shedding phenomena,

the Strouhal number, see Section 2.3.3 shows that $T \propto \text{size}/(\text{St} \cdot V_{\text{eff}})$ meaning a longer measurement time is needed for a larger turbine, while the measurement time becomes shorter for the rare higher wind speeds (Note that the rotational velocity component is lacking so that the effective velocity has become equal to the free stream wind speed). In the New Mexico experiment standstill experiments at a tunnel speed of 30 m/s and a rotor with a diameter of 4.5 m, a time of 5 seconds was sufficient to investigate the vortex shedding phenomena. This suggests that a measurement time of approximately $5 \cdot (D/4.5) \cdot (30/V_w)$ seconds would be suitable for an experiment on a rotor with diameter D and wind speed V_w .

3.3 Frequency response of pressure measurements at standstill: Some considerations

Basically the consideration on the sampling frequency for standstill measurements remain unchanged from the considerations given for rotating conditions, see section 2.3.3. However as mentioned above the rotational velocity component is lacking which makes the effective velocity lower (even at storm conditions the high wind speed generally does not compensate the lack of rotational velocity). Then equation 6 yields a lower sampling frequency and associated longer measurement time.

3.4 Accuracy of pressure measurements at standstill: Some considerations

In section 2.3.2 it is mentioned that sensors should be selected with a range such that they operate in the upper end of the range where the accuracy is highest. This selection is generally based on expected pressures at rotational conditions. The lower effective velocities at standstill yields lower pressure levels. Consequently, the resulting low pressure levels fall within the lower part of the pressure transducer range, where uncertainties are significantly higher. The measurement accuracy of the TIADE pressure sensors (p_{acc}) was specified by the manufacturer and turned out to be 8 Pa. As mentioned in section 2.3.2 the accuracy p_{acc} is interpreted as follows: $p_{\text{meas}} - p_{\text{acc}} < p_{\text{real}} < p_{\text{meas}} + p_{\text{acc}}$ hence the real pressure is between the measured pressure +/- the measurement accuracy. In section 2.3.2 it is also mentioned that the pressure distribution is often targeted to be measured within an uncertainty of 10% of the dynamic pressure q : $0.5\rho V_{\text{eff}}^2$. In the case of 8Pa accuracy this implies that the dynamic pressure should be larger than 80 Pa corresponding to a free stream wind speed of 12 m/s or higher. However section 2.3.2 also mentions experiments where an uncertainty of 1% is targeted which would require a dynamic pressures of 800 Pa corresponding to a very high wind speed of 36 m/s.

3.5 Considerations on angle of attack reference velocity, and location of pressure ports at standstill

While the above sections highlight several issues that are more challenging in standstill conditions compared to rotating conditions, there are also certain aspects that become less complex.

This holds amongst others for the angle of attack which is complex for rotating conditions (see section 2.7) but which for rotating conditions, in principle, can be determined straightforwardly from the incoming wind direction and the twist(+ pitch angle). However, even in standstill conditions, there is a trailed wake induction that needs to be considered. This can be modeled using established lifting line methods for finite three-dimensional wings as known from aeronautics. These methods represent the wing as a bound vortex with associated trailing vortices that induce a velocity near each blade section. Such methods were already applied in the early 1990's [64].

Additionally, the determination of reference pressure, which complicates the definition of aerodynamic coefficients in a rotating experiment (see Section 2.6.1), becomes more straightforward. The absence of a pressure jump across the rotor plane (see Figure 19) allows the reference pressure to be taken as the ambient pressure near the turbine.

In Section 2.2, methods are described to determine the optimal placement of pressure sensors along the airfoil to achieve the highest accuracy in measuring pressure distribution and resulting aerodynamic loads across a wide range of angles of attack under rotating conditions. These methods could, in principle, also include pressure distributions at standstill in the optimization process. However, since pressure distributions at standstill can differ significantly from those in rotating conditions, this might significantly impact the optimal sensor layout. While standstill conditions are important, rotating conditions are generally considered even more critical. Therefore, it makes sense to give the pressure

distributions under rotating conditions the highest priority when optimizing the layout of pressure sensors.

4 Aero-elastic model input: Confidentiality issues

It is stated before that aerodynamic experiments need be done in open research. Public in this sense does not only mean that the measurement data have to be released, but for validation purposes it is equally important that the underlying turbine model description is published as well. In the present context, the aerodynamic and aeroelastic blade data are most essential. Usually those data are protected and if it all available this will require years long negotiations (as was the case with the DANAERO experiment in IEA Tasks 29/47). A potential solution to determine the outer blade geometry, i.e. the aerodynamic input is offered by scanning or photographing the blade geometry by the experimental party, see sections 4.1 and 4.2. These solutions have potential in case the instrumented turbine is owned by the measurement party or in case the experiment is carried out in cooperation with a turbine owner. The need for knowing the structural data is discussed in section 4.3. As long-term solution, a large-scale, collaborative aerodynamic experiment is proposed in section 4.4.

4.1 Aerodynamic blade input: Scanning the blade geometry

Ecole Centrale Nantes scanned the aerodynamic shape of the blade on which aerodynamic measurements are performed.

4.1.1 Scan methods

There exist numerous approaches to scan a blade. Two approaches are presented below: one approach is from the ground with the blades on the turbine where the other was done during maintenance with the rotor on the ground. Both approaches were subcontracted to an Expert-Surveyor firm, which for both methods used the same scanning laser 3D techniques, with an accuracy down to $\pm 3\text{mm}$. Both methods present advantages and disadvantages that are detailed below.

From the ground

It is possible to perform a scan method from the ground so that blades could stay mounted on the turbine. However, different inconveniences should be pointed out. The first one is related to the weather conditions. Even with low winds there were still some blade movements which increased of the dispersion in the cloud of measurement points. Consequently, a non-unique blade shape is extracted. The second inconvenience lies in the fact that the mast can hide parts of the blades during the scanning process, which gives holes in the cloud of measurement points. This prevents the extraction of the entire 3D blade properties. The last inconvenience is the difficulty to find out how the blades were mounted on the hub: pre-cone and tilt angles (see figure 23).

Figure 23: Scheme of the angle between the root blade axis and the rotor plane (pre-cone angle) and of the angle between the horizontal axis and the shaft axis (tilt angle) modified from [65].

The evaluation of the tilt angle needs a scan of the whole nacelle with the mast and the floor for horizontal reference. And extraction of the pre-cone angle needs the knowledge of the rotor plane with the hub. This should be anticipated in the scanning strategy. From this method, we extracted one 2D blade section shape at 82% of the rotor diameter that was extruded, manufactured and installed in the CSTB wind tunnel (see [66, 67]).

During maintenance with the rotor on the ground

Another method consists of scanning the full rotor during a rotor maintenance. Compared to the previous scan method, materials were added to prevent the blade from moving such as caps at the blade tip or lanyards. This prevents measurements at these locations and induces errors in the measured pre-bend angle distribution. Also, we cannot measure the tilt angle. As for the first scan method, no-wind weather conditions should be targeted. It should be pointed out that the blade is inside the hub at collar location within a distance that cannot be retrieved from the scan (see the collar location in figure 24). Therefore, the total measured length is slightly smaller than the actual blade length given by the blade manufacturer.

Figure 24: a) photograph of the blade-hub junction marked by a collar. b) Cloud of measurement points with the reference surface collar at the blade root.

4.1.2 Post-processing of cloud data

The post-processing of cloud data can be subcontracted by the Expert-Surveyor firm who does the scan. However, it was found important to clearly communicate with them the procedure to extract the blade properties and especially the framework used.

The hub and blade frameworks

To extract the pre-cone angle, there is a need to define the hub framework (see figure 25a and b). From the knowledge of the circular shapes at the blade root, it is possible to extract the blade root axis of the three blades composing the rotor. The intersection of these axis define the hub origin, O_{hub} . The rotor plane is defined by a plane parallel to the floor containing the hub origin. The angle from the rotor plane to the blade axis is the pre-cone angle. To extract the blade sections, there is a need to define a blade origin. It was found convenient to define it at the flat surface of the collar (see figure 25c). The transformation between the hub and blade frameworks can be used to set the blades relatively to the hub.

Extraction of blade sections

Once the blade framework is set, it is possible to extract blade sections along the sweep and pre-bend lines (see figure 26). It can be performed manually by local readjustments along the local chord axis from local identification of the leading and trailing edges. This ensures that sections are extracted normal to the sweep and pre-bend lines. The 3D blade is generally made of around 10 sections. Extracting 45 sections (Remark Gerard: But you did it at 10 sections??) is found sufficient to describe the sweep and pre-bend lines, the local twist angle and the airfoil sections composing the blade.

Figure 25: Definition of framework: a) Hub Top view. Dotted blue lines are blade root axis. b) Rotor on the floor. z_h and x_h axis are part of the hub framework. c) Side view of the hub. O_{blade} is the blade framework origin which starts at the reference collar surface.

This last process has been performed by [68] with a very good agreement with the manufacturer's information.

4.1.3 Accuracy evaluation

It is difficult to assess the accuracy without a priori knowledge of the blade properties. Still it is, at least to some extent possible to evaluate the uncertainty by comparing the different scans. From the two scan methods described in section 4.1.1, it was possible to extract two sections at 80% of the rotor diameter from a 2MW turbine (see figure 27). They were identified to be close to a Naca 63(3)418 profile with a modified thickness and camber (see tabular 3). Scans were thus found accurate enough to identify the airfoil family and associated aerodynamic properties.

Another indication from the uncertainty comes from the Expert-Surveyor firm, which promised an accuracy down to $\pm 3\text{mm}$. This can be compared with the maximum thickness of the airfoil which is ??? mm.

Table 3: Airfoil shape parameters.

From	Max Thickness [%]	at x/c [%]	Max Camber [%]	at x/c [%]
First Scan	19.84	32.9	3.83	51.60
Second Scan	20.58	35.58	3.66	47.27
Identified Naca	20.5	33.9	3.5	50

4.2 Aerodynamic blade input: Photographing the blade

Another option to obtain the blade geometry is using photogrammetry. This method is probably more adequate to retrieve local blade section geometry but might require more work than scanning for the complete profile. This method can be done by anyone with a decent camera. Photogrammetry is often used to scan a terrain using drones or airplanes, but it can also be used to scan small or large objects. The concept is relatively simple: Specific object points is seen in a 2D plan on a photo as an image point. Each image point on each photo creates a line with the focal point of the camera, on which the object point could be localised, because the depth is missing on one photo. But with multiple photos, by triangulating all these lines, the 3D position of the object point can be calculated (see figure 28).

Figure 26: The sweep and pre-bend lines along which blade sections are extracted.

Figure 27: Airfoil section: a) comparison between scans, b) comparison with the identified airfoil section.

Now, instead of one point but multiple points from speckled patterns or salient points placed on the blade, it is possible to recreate the 3D shape of a blade. Two methods are here possible:

Few points with few high quality photos Specific points are defined on the blade, and interpolation are made between these points to recreate an airfoil using spline or Bézier curves for example. It has been used for example on a 68m^2 sail on water [69], where 6 photos were used to define the position of 60 points. These points called "coded targets" are printed and placed on the object. They are automatically identified by the algorithm. In that case, the software used was Photomodeler² with an accuracy obtained of less than 3%. In this method, the angles between the photos need to be quite large (about 40°) to avoid the lines of sight of each image point to be close to each other, nearly parallel.

Many points with few high quality photos The second methods uses speckled patterns and many photos that are close to each other with a lot of overlap and redundancy. With this method, the algorithm detects pattern on one photo and look for this pattern on the other photos. The view between the photos must therefore be similar with about 60 to 80% of overlapping and little angles between the photos (less than 10°). For this method, many photos need to be taken (about 500) with speckled patterns (like white noise images). This method works well on a textured object, which is not necessarily the case for wind turbine blades.

For example in the Aerosense project [24], pressure sensors were installed on a 7kW wind turbine. As the sensors were installed manually, it was required to know the position of the shape of the blade and also the position of the pressure sensors. A GoPro installed on the helmet of the person installing the sensor node on the blade, filmed the complete installation of the pressure sensors on the blade.

²<https://www.photomodeler.com>

Figure 28: Principle of photogrammetry using triangulation. Several object-points are projected onto different image planes (photographs).

Figure 29: Steps of the blade reconstruction using photogrammetry

More than 500 photographs were extracted from this video to be used in the software 3DFZephyr³. The housing of the sensor nodes were finely decorated to give extra texture that could be used by the algorithm. Papers of white noise were printed and placed on the blade to give more texture to the blade where the sensors were not installed. More than 50 000 points were detected with this first process (figure 29a), which was then used to create a dense point cloud (figure 29b) and then a mesh (figure 29c). With that many photos and points, the orientation of the photos are automatically determined during the reconstruction by minimising the errors. A relative accuracy given by the reconstruction algorithm with a root-mean-square error of 0.76 mm. The position of the sensors, and other known distances were taken from this model to quantify the accuracy of the 3D reconstruction. The range of errors is from -1.15 mm to 0.82 mm, with an absolute average of 0.14 mm. The chord length of the section is 355 mm, which means the blade shape and the positions of the sensors have an accuracy below 0.5% of the chord.

A 3D reconstruction of the blade is presented in figure 30. On the tested 6kW wind turbine, some edges and areas where the blade has no texture seem not that well reconstructed (figure 30a), but the interesting areas, such as the sensor nodes are correctly reconstructed with smooth surfaces

³<https://www.3dflow.net/3df-zephyr-photogrammetry-software/>

Figure 30: 3D reconstruction of the blade shape with the sensors.

(figure 30b). The photography method is therefore adequate for local shape measurement on a wind turbine blade (coverage of about 1 to 2m spanwise). From such model, it is possible to extract the blade section. However, with the photogrammetry process, it is hardly possible to determine the general geometry of the blade such as the overall twist, pre-bend and sweep of the blade.

4.3 Structural input

The methods described in sections 4.1 and 4.2 show promising results to generate the aerodynamic input i.e. the outer part of the blade. However a good validation of aerodynamic models requires a full aero-elastic model due to the interaction of aerodynamic properties with the aero-elasticity from structural effects. The importance of having a reliable aero-elastic model description increases with size. This is illustrated by the aero-elastic simulations on the 15 MW Reference Wind Turbine as done in Task 47. They show, even at a moderate wind speed, a torsional deformation in the order of 2 degrees which obviously has a very large impact on the aerodynamics of this turbine and so the aero-acoustics.

Generating a reliable aero-elastic input is very challenging, If the experimenting party owns the turbine and the blades are (very) small it may be relatively easy to determine the mass, centre of gravity and some first eigenfrequencies can be determined relatively easy by weighting, balancing a vibration test with accelerometers but for larger wind turbines this requires a well equipped aero-elastic testing lab.

4.4 Proposal for a public aerodynamic experiment

The previous considerations make clear that the restrictions on sharing turbine model data form a significant challenge in analyzing measurement data. This limitation hampers a joint analysis, even though such shared analysis has proven highly beneficial in past projects. Therefore, there is an urgent need for a public aerodynamic field experiment on a large-scale wind turbine, utilizing the most advanced aerodynamic measurement techniques. This experiment should be conducted by a large consortium involving many members of the research community. Some considerations for such experiment are:

- Scale An important requirement lies on the scale of the turbine. Turbine scale is sometimes expressed in terms of rated power but it should be realised that rated power has an ambiguous relation to scale where turbines can have a large variety of power densities For aerodynamic

modelling, rotor size is more important than rated power. This scale dependency relates to Reynolds number and the relationship between atmospheric inflow scales and turbine scales. Larger deflections also make aerodynamic response modeling more challenging. A minimal rotor diameter of 150 meters, with a chord-based Reynolds number above 12 million, is (somewhat arbitrarily) suggested.

- Location (on-shore versus off-shore) A turbine at an onshore location is preferred for this experiment. Detailed experiments require access to the blade for mounting sensors and instruments, which is not feasible offshore. While offshore inflow conditions differ from onshore, most relevant phenomena such as shear, turbulence, etc can be studied onshore.
- Measurement time: Data should be collected over at least two years to ensure statistical certainty and capture rare atmospheric conditions and their aerodynamic responses (e.g., extreme shears, incoherent structures). A long measurement period also allows for incorporating lessons learned in the early phases of the experiment into later campaigns, justifying the large investment.

Ideally, this experiment should be conducted on an existing large-scale turbine with publicly available data. An older but still relevant platform could be declassified and used as a research turbine. Alternatively, the research community should find access to a turbine that serves as a testbed on which the existing blades are replaced by custom-designed blades which meet the research needs. This approach allows the research consortium to retain ownership of the blade data, thus overcoming confidentiality issues, even though the blades are manufactured by a blade manufacturer. A remaining confidentiality issue in such a project might involve the turbine data. However, for aerodynamic purposes, turbine data are less critical than blade data, although an issue could arise with the control algorithm. If the algorithm cannot be released and NDAs are not feasible, using measured rotor speed and pitch angle as functions of time and wind speed might suffice.

Although such a public experiment will be expensive, it is justified by the importance of the issue. Collaborating with other IEA Tasks could further justify the expense, as the problem of restricted turbine model data also appears in other Tasks. For example, IEA Task 39, which considers wind turbine acoustics, also relies on accurate aerodynamic blade input, making this experiment beneficial for both research areas.

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